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Cradle-to-Grave Life Cycle Assessment and Carbon Footprint Analysis of Narrow Body Commercial Aircraft towards Sustainable Aviation

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Thanks to...

Above all, I would like to thank those who have never stunted in their support since my childhood, my father and mother 'Recep and Döndü Çobanoğlu". I could not have achieved most of my successes without their love and dedication. Throughout my life, I have been blessed with an incredible family and a circle of friends whose unwavering sincerity and support have helped shape me into the person I am today. Lastly, I owe a debt of gratitude to all the teachers and lecturers, including my supervisor, Dr Leticia Ozawa-Meida, who have brought me to where I am today and made me an engineer passionate about my profession, without sparing their knowledge, effort, and patience throughout my educational journey.

Abstract

This dissertation provides a cradle-to-grave Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and carbon footprint analysis of narrow-body commercial aircraft, with a focus specifically on the Airbus A320 family. The study complies with ISO 14040/44 practices and uses PRISMA-directed data gathering to examine three major stages of the life cycle: manufacturing, operational, and end-of-life phase. At the production stage, the investigation encompassed raw materials extraction, intermediate forms, and final assembly, with a particular focus on aluminium alloys and carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP), which were found both to have substantial embodied energy and GHG emissions.

The operational phase was assessed based on the Well-to-Wake (WTW), Well-to-Tank (WTT), and Tank-to-Wake (TTW) frameworks, which cover Landing and Take-Off (LTO) cycles, cruise phase emissions, as well as maintenance activities. Results show that combustion of the fuel during the operational life is the main cause of life cycle emissions, accounting for a large share of aircraft carbon footprint. Yet manufacturing impacts are also significant, mostly because composite materials are used, while end-of-life activities, such as recycling, provide credits which only partly compensate for total impacts.

Comparisons between various engine options showed significant differences in lifetime emissions. Newer engine technologies improved efficiency, but they weren't enough to change the operational dominance. The study also puts its results in the context of global rules, such as ICAO's CORSIA scheme, United Nations Sustainability Development Goals, the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), and IATA's promise to reach net-zero emissions by 2050.

The research highlights the crucial role of sustainable aviation fuels (SAF), advanced propulsion systems, and circular economy strategies in mitigating aviation's environmental impact. This dissertation enhances the discourse on sustainable aviation by delivering a comprehensive environmental profile of narrow-body aircraft, offering pragmatic insights for policymakers, manufacturers, and operators seeking to align the industry with global climate objectives.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CFRP	Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer
CO	Carbon monoxide
CORSIA	Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EIA	Environmentally Impact Assessment
EOL	End-of-life
Eq	Equivalent
EU UTS	European Union Emissions Trading System
G	Giga (10^9)
gCO ₂	Gram Carbon dioxide
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GJ	Gigajoule
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HC	Hydrocarbons
IATA	International Air Transport Association
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
ILCD	International Life Cycle Data System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Standards Organisation
J	Joule
Kg	Kilogram
kgCO ₂	Kilogram Carbon dioxide
Kt	Kiloton
KWh	Kilowatt Hour
kN	Kilonewton
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LTO	Landing Take-Off Cycle
M	Mega (10^6)
Mj	Megajoule
Mmt	Million metric tons
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxide
PAX	Passenger
SAF	Sustainable Aviation Fuel
t	Ton
tCO ₂	Ton Carbon dioxide
TTW	Tank-to-Wake
UN SDG	United Nations Sustainability Development Goals
WTT	Well-to-Tank
WTW	Well-to-Wake

Chapter 1: Introduction

The commercial aviation sector represents a growing share of the global transportation industry. Commercial aviation, regulated globally by the International Air Transport Association (IATA) and the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), remains the preferred mode of transport while travelling long distances due to technological advancements and enhanced safety standards [1]. It is at the forefront of mobility choices, because it is a fast and safe choice. The number of flight and passengers, which decreased on a global scale due to health measures during the pandemic period, is remarkably close to the pre-pandemic period with total 4.2 billion passengers and 35.25 million departures in 2023. Data from June 2025 indicates that 4.8 billion passengers travelled in 2024, more than in the pre-pandemic period. In Figure 1 and Figure 2 these quantitative amounts are shown.

Figure 1 Global Traffic of Flight Departures (millions) [1]

Figure 2 Global Traffic of Passengers (billion) [2]

IATA includes 341 airlines in 120 countries, representing more than 82% of global air traffic. This number includes the main airlines that operate large-scale and international flights. IATA's member list includes the most established and major players in the industry . Total worldwide fleet size currently counts 28,674 aircraft, with 23,513 active and 5,161 grounded [3]. A little over 14,350 of these aircraft are Airbus, and over 10,000 are Boeing . These numbers demonstrate that the two largest manufacturers in the commercial aircraft industry are Airbus and Boeing. Airbus, headquartered in Europe, and Boeing, based in the United States, are long-standing competitors and dominate the narrow-body aircraft market[2], [4].

Table 1 illustrates that most of the total commercial aircraft fleet consists of single-aisle passenger aircraft. Airbus' A320 family (A318, A319, A320, A321) dominates the industry with 11,563 aircraft. The most widely used aircraft model in this family is the A320. The A320 family consists of two primary variants: the A320ceo (current engine option) and the A320neo (new engine option).

Aircraft Model	Quantity
A320 Family	11563
A300/A310	257
A330	1467
A340	187
A350	662
A380	216

Table 1 Fleet Size in Operation [5]

1.1. Relevance of the Project

The aviation industry is under growing pressure to minimise its environmental effects and carbon footprint. Though much attention has been given to emissions for operations, achieving full understanding and calculation of emissions throughout the life cycle assessment LCA stages continue to be a major challenge. Global aircraft manufacturer Airbus is committing to reaching net-zero carbon emissions by 2050, with ambitious interim targets to cut emissions from operational commercial aircraft. Airbus has set remarkable and concrete sustainability and environmental goals. It aims to achieve 100% Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) capacity in commercial Airbus aircraft by 2030, while also committing to reducing CO₂ emissions by 46% by 2035. It also aims to become a net-zero company by 2050 [6].

According to a study by Klöwer's [7], the commercial aviation sector is responsible for approximately 2.4% of annual global CO₂ emissions, this figure rises to 4% when non-CO₂ impacts such as high-altitude water vapor, NO_x emissions, and condensate traces are included. According to the study, aviation has contributed approximately 0.05°C to global temperatures to date, and this value is estimated to reach 0.1°C by 2050. If current growth trends continue, aviation could consume between 6% and 17% of the remaining carbon budget toward the 1.5–2°C global warming target. Among the proposed strategies to reduce the sector's climate impact, a 2.5% reduction in annual air traffic or the use of 90% carbon-neutral fuels by 2050 are prominent [7].

The aviation sector is actively taking measures to reduce its environmental impact in line with global climate goals. The ICAO's 2016 launch of the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) is one of the major global initiatives. CORSIA seeks to cap the net CO₂ emissions from international flights at 2020 levels [8].

Airlines that operate in the European Economic Area are subject to yearly carbon caps set by the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS)[9]. In order to provide a financial incentive to reduce emissions, airlines that exceed their emission allowances are required to purchase carbon credits.

In addition, the IATA declared in 2021 to have the world's aviation sector achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2050 [10]. This challenging goal is in line with the Paris Agreement's objectives to keep global warming to less than 2°C. A variety of mitigation strategies, such as greater use of Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF), next-generation aircraft technologies, operational enhancements, and market-based initiatives, will be needed to accomplish this.

These commitments reflect a growing recognition within the aviation industry of its role in combating climate change and a move toward more sustainable air travel.

Globally located commercial airline companies prefer most of their operational aircrafts from Boeing and Airbus SE which have dominated the aircraft manufacturing sector. These two famous rivals are not just basically competing; they also make each other grow day by day [4]. The narrow-body aircrafts are the most common and widely used models in commercial aviation, especially the Boeing 737 and Airbus A320 . In this report, A320 will be taken the centre of LCA approach and assessment.

1.2. Problem Definition and Contribution of the Study

The existing published research offers a basic understanding of how aviation impacts the environment. Research has examined the life cycle assessment (LCA) of airplanes and shown that production can contribute up to 15% of GHG emissions, while the operational phase takes responsibility for the major proportions . The research also looked at how logistics and material development impact emissions for narrow-body aircraft, indicating that while green technology may reduce environmental effects, creative designs are required to reach the challenging 2050 targets. To assess sustainability, the A320 production line has also been subjected to integrated Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and LCA techniques. There is still a huge research deficit, nonetheless. For the Airbus A320 platform, there is presently no integrated life cycle assessment model that specifically separates and segments cradle-to-grave emissions. By examining research on cradle-to-grave life cycle assessment (LCA) with an emphasis on emissions for the Airbus A320, this study seeks to close this crucial gap and offer insightful information for aviation decarbonization initiatives.

Despite numerous studies addressing aviation-related emissions, most existing research either narrowly focuses on specific phases (e.g. flight operations, individual components, such as engines or materials, cruise phase) without offering a universal view. In particular, comprehensive cradle-to-grave Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) of individual aircraft models remain rare, fragmented, or outdated. However, there is currently no single study that consolidates all relevant LCA data which includes manufacturing, operation, maintenance, and end-of-life (EoL) into an accessible, updated, and comparative review.

This dissertation seeks to fill this gap by providing an integrative and up-to-date systematic review of the A320 platform's full life cycle. It combines previously scattered data with current industry trends and technological updates (such as current data, latest reports and test results) to form a unified and practical reference point for industry professionals and policymakers working on aviation sustainability.

1.3. Aim and Objectives

The aim is assessing GHG emissions in line with sustainable aviation objectives by analysing cradle-to-grave Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) research in the Airbus A320's manufacturing, operational phase and end-of-life (EoL) stages. While conducting technical and quantitative analysis, a synthesis will be carried out with data obtained from various sources and literature. The analysis will be conducted using publicly available data and data obtained from the literature. Primary data will not be used to avoid violating companies' privacy rights. Despite the extensive literature in aviation, there is a lack of a comparable, understandable, and interpretable cradle-to-grave LCA report for the widely used A320 aircraft. This research aims to fill this gap by implementing the following objectives.

- To conduct a comprehensive literature analysis in accordance with the PRISMA framework to obtain up-to-date secondary data for precise inputs for LCA.
- To identify CO₂-eq during the production, assembly, transport, operational use, maintenance, and end-of-life phases to present alternative development.
- To assess the sustainability and GHG emissions of currently used alternative technologies. An emissions assessment will be conducted for the operational use of the CFM-LEAP-1A and PW1127G engines, developed as an alternative to the CFM56 used in the classic A320 aircraft and used in the A320neo (new engine option).
- To provide recommendations to reduce environmental impacts based on the synthesis of a comprehensive and detail LCA study.

1.4. Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals

The present study provides a comprehensive and up-to-date environmental performance evaluation of the Airbus A320 aircraft, which contributes to the achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). As a reference for sustainable aviation initiatives, it fills up the current knowledge gaps [11].

SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure

Target 9.4: By evaluating narrow-body aircraft's environmental performance and identifying operational and design innovations that improve fuel economy and lower emissions, the study aids in the aviation industry's shift to low-carbon and resource-efficient infrastructure by assessing clean aviation technologies using life cycle assessment.

Target 9.5: This study advances SDG 9.5 by producing knowledge and analysis that promotes eco-innovation in aviation engineering through its life-cycle-based methodology and systematic literature review. The results offer a solid scientific basis for upcoming advancements in sustainability reporting and aircraft lifecycle emissions.

SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production

Target 12.2: By analysing the use of materials (such as Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer and aluminium) and assessing the possibility of recycling and reusing them at the end of the aircraft's life. In the aerospace sector, it promotes circular economy techniques for sustainable resource management.

Target 12.4: The cradle-to-grave LCA approach directly addresses SDG 12.4 by analysing the full environmental burden of aircraft, including emissions and waste generation across all life stages. This enables better understanding of environmental impacts and their reduction.

Target 12.5: By incorporating end-of-life techniques like disassembly, material recovery, and reuse, the study helps aviation reduce waste and advances SDG 12.5.

SDG 13: Climate Action

Target 13.2: This research contributes to SDG 13.2 by providing quantitative insights on GHG emissions from aircraft and identifying low-emission technologies. The findings inform aviation policy development and support international climate targets, such as those set by ICAO and the Paris Agreement.

Target 13.3: By increasing awareness among stakeholders (academia, policymakers, engineers) of aviation's climate impact and the importance of life cycle thinking in mitigation planning.

1.5. Outline

There are six chapters in this dissertation. The study's background, significance, and main goals are presented in Chapter 1, along with how it relates to the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The basics of life cycle assessment (LCA), aviation-specific regulations, previous LCA studies, and pertinent climate change mitigation strategies are all covered in detail in Chapter 2's literature review. The research methodology, including the PRISMA systematic review procedure and the LCA framework, is described in Chapter 3. The conclusions from secondary data and evaluation outcomes from all phases of the A320's life cycle are summarised in Chapter 4. A critical analysis and summary of the possible effects of different mitigation techniques are given in Chapter 5. The dissertation is finally concluded in Chapter 6 with important conclusions, restrictions, and suggestions for additional study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter reviews the literature on life cycle assessment (LCA) in aviation, covering regulatory frameworks, previous studies, and mitigation strategies. It highlights key findings, research gaps, and sets the foundation for the dissertation's analysis.

2.1. ISO 14040/44 Framework for Life Cycle Assessment

ISO 14040/44 defines life cycle assessment (LCA) as a methodical approach to evaluate environmental factors and possible impacts throughout a product's lifecycle, from the extraction of raw materials (cradle) to production, operation, and end-of-life disposal (grave) or recycling (cradle) [12]. Four stages make up the typical LCA framework:

1. *Goal and Scope Definition*: This includes defining the study's purpose, establishing system boundaries (e.g., cradle-to-grave or cradle-to-gate). In this study, the functional unit is selected per Airbus A320 aircraft (life-time) and per 1 passenger-km(pkm) (see Section 3.2 for details).
2. *Inventory Analysis (LCI)*: It involves gathering numerical information on energy consumption, emissions, waste, and material inputs during every stage of the life cycle.
3. *Impact Assessment (LCIA)*: Converts inventory results into environmental impact indicators like Global Warming Potential (GWP, CO₂-eq), acidification, eutrophication, photochemical smog, human toxicity, and resource depletion.
4. *Interpretation*: Combines results to determine important impact contributors, assess the quality of the data, and create recommendations while taking sensitivity and uncertainty analyses into account.

This methodological structure allows organizations and researchers to benchmark and compare environmental performance of products, technologies, or systems. Illustration of the general phases of a life cycle assessment, as described by ISO 14040 is presented on Figure 3. While ISO provides an overall framework, the aviation industry is dependent on particular laws and regulations that affect LCA practice.

Figure 3 LCA Phases [12]

2.2. Regulations and Standards Relevant to the Aviation Industry

This section explains the main regulations and standards in aviation. These provide the framework for how environmental impacts are assessed and managed in the industry.

2.2.1. ICAO Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation

CORSIA is a global market-based scheme developed by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) to address carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from international aviation. It was formally adopted in 2016 as part of ICAO's Global Market-Based Measure strategy, and it represents the first global mechanism to regulate CO₂ emissions from a specific sector of the economy [8].

CORSIA's main aim is to stabilise net CO₂ emissions at 2020 levels for international flights by requiring airlines to offset the growth in emissions below 2020's levels. While domestic flights fall under national or regional schemes (like EU ETS), CORSIA exclusively covers international aviation emissions, which account for over 65% of aviation-related CO₂ globally. As of 2025, 124 states voluntarily participate in CORSIA, including the UK, US, EU countries, Türkiye, and many others [8].

2.2.2. European Green Deal & European Union Aviation Safety Agency Initiatives

The European Green Deal, adopted in December 2019 by the European Commission, serves as a strategic roadmap to make the EU's economy sustainable by turning climate and environmental challenges into opportunities. A primary goal is to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by the year 2050 [13]. The aviation industry is classified as a "hard-to-abate" sector in this framework because of its dependence on fossil fuels and its rapidly rising demand, leading to lifecycle-wide assessments and innovative mitigation techniques.

The European Green Deal emphasises "lifecycle thinking" in policy design and technology development. This includes:

- Mandatory environmental impact assessments (EIA) for infrastructure projects (e.g., airports).
- Promotion of eco-design and circular economy principles in industrial product development.
- Creation of standardised, harmonised LCA databases for critical industries (EcoInvent, International Life Cycle Data System - ILCD).
- Implementation of carbon pricing and trading mechanisms that reflect upstream lifecycle emissions (e.g., through the EU ETS).
- Targeting modal shifts toward rail and low-emission aviation.

The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) is the central regulatory body supporting the Green Deal in the context of aviation. Conventionally focused on suitability to fly and safety. EASA has expanded its mandate to environmental certification and sustainability assessment through the European Aviation Environmental Report (EAER), published in cooperation with the European Environment Agency (EEA) and EUROCONTROL. Key EASA initiatives include [14]:

- Aircraft environmental labelling based on CO₂ and noise performance.
- Monitoring fuel efficiency trends and SAF uptake in European fleets.
- Supporting eco-design requirements in new aircraft through type certification.

- Encouraging recycling and dismantling best practices via research under Clean Sky and Horizon Europe projects.

The EASA [15] states that between 2013 and 2019, aviation CO₂ emissions rose by 5% yearly, while NO_x emissions increased by 4% annually. The inclusion of cradle-to-grave life cycle assessment (LCA) into airline and manufacturer-level sustainability reporting is specifically called for in the report. Under these regulations and laws, the aviation industry must show transparent and measurable progress using internationally recognised assessment methods like ISO 14040/44-compliant LCA.

Although there is not a certain aviation-specific LCA standard like ISO, practitioners frequently integrate ISO frameworks with databases particular to the sector, including EcoInvent, and frequently require customised process entries for aircraft manufacturing and materials.

2.3. Previous Research on LCA Studies

While the body of existing literature offers a fundamental understanding of the environmental implications in aviation, a thorough, cradle-to-grave GHG footprint analysis for particular aircraft platforms, such as the Airbus A320, is still critically lacking [16]. An extensive life cycle assessment (LCA) of the Airbus A320 was carried out by Howe, Kolios, and Brennan [17], who found that although the operational phase accounts for the majority of an aircraft's GHG emissions, the manufacturing phase can account for as much as 15%. This includes impacts from the production of composite and aluminium materials, and component transportation between Airbus facilities.

Although the main emphasis is on the operational and upstream manufacturing stages, Howe, Kolios, and Brennan's [17] study uses a cradle-to-grave system boundary structure to apply a life cycle assessment to commercial jet airliners. As opposed to a model-specific analysis, the functional unit used in this study is defined per aircraft, enabling comparisons across various aircraft types. The authors estimated material composition, fuel usage, and emissions primarily from secondary data sources, such as EcoInvent databases and published literature. Global warming potential (GWP), where operating emissions predominated, was the most important environmental impact found. Emissions from the manufacturing phase of composite and aluminium production followed second. However, recycling methods and end-of-life scenarios were not fully taken into consideration in the study.

Kolios [18] established a cradle-to-gate system boundary by focussing exclusively on the Airbus A320 manufacturing phase. Examining material flows and energy inputs per aircraft, the functional unit is based on a single A320 airframe. Using primary and secondary data, such as manufacturing process data and environmental databases like EcoInvent, the study applies process-based life cycle assessment (LCA). Important materials were evaluated, including titanium, carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP), and aluminium. GWP, cumulative energy demand, and material-specific emissions are the primary environmental effects. The authors discovered that, despite its weight-loss benefits, CFRP production was the manufacturing process with the highest greenhouse gas emissions, underscoring a crucial trade-off between sustainable manufacturing and lightweight design [18].

The study by Bravo, Vieira, and Ferrer [19] worked on a partial LCA model with system boundaries focused on the production and operational phases of narrow-body aircraft, using aircraft similar to the A320. The functional unit was not clearly stated but can be inferred as

emissions per aircraft or per flight hour based on modelling assumptions. The study utilized computational LCA tools and a mix of scenario-based and simulation data, including logistics pathways, material innovations, and energy consumption estimates. The environmental impacts analysed include GWP and energy use, with the results showing that incorporating greener logistics and advanced materials significantly reduces emissions. Yet, the study highlighted that achieving 2050 emission targets requires deeper design innovations beyond incremental material changes.

A scenario-based life cycle assessment (LCA) of the Airbus A320 was carried out by Lewis (2013) using a well-to-wake system boundary. Lewis's LCA focused on the operational phase across three flight profiles: short-, medium-, and long-haul. It included emissions from fuel extraction, production, distribution, and combustion during flights (well-to-wake). In order to assess emissions efficiency across flight types, the functional unit was defined as CO₂ emissions per passenger-kilometre. The study's data sources included ICAO emission coefficients, fuel consumption data, and flight performance simulations. GWP was the primary environmental impact evaluated, and the findings showed that medium-haul flights demonstrated superior fuel and emissions efficiency, while short-haul flights produced disproportionately high emissions because of the frequent take-off and landing cycles [20]. However, the study did not consider upstream manufacturing emissions or end-of-life stages.

Spagnulo [21] employed a hybrid Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach to perform a combined sustainability analysis for the A320 production line. The system boundary extended from the extraction of raw materials to early operational use, but it did not fully include end-of-life processes. The functional unit was framed as "per aircraft system," with an emphasis on environmental and economic performance. Literature-based emissions factors, industry reports, and enterprise-level simulations were used to gather data. Energy consumption and recycling rates are among the environmental effects that are examined. While a comprehensive cradle-to-grave assessment is still lacking, the study found that circular design strategies (such as remanufacturing and materials reuse) can significantly improve both cost-efficiency and environmental performance [21].

Despite these valuable contributions, a critical research gap remains due to the lack of a consolidated LCA model specifically isolating and segmenting cradle-to-grave emissions for the Airbus A320 platform. Past research and literature have largely focused on specific phases, and a comprehensive report is lacking. This research will utilize and combine data from the literature to develop a comprehensive and interpretational overview LCA for the A320.

2.3.1. Climate Change Mitigation Strategies in the Aviation Industry

The aviation sector has looked into a number of ways to reduce its impact on the climate in response to growing environmental concerns. One important strategy is the use of substitute lightweight materials, like carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP), which lower aircraft weight and hence fuel consumption. But there is a sustainability trade-off because these materials also require a lot of energy to produce [18].

Alternative fuels, particularly Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF), have emerged as a key solution. SAFs can reduce life-cycle emissions by up to 80% compared to the conventional Jet-A1 fuel, depending on the feedstock and production method [22]. Airbus and Boeing have both committed to achieving 100% SAF capability across their fleets by 2030 [23]

Innovations in technology also play a big role. Because of better thermodynamic cycles and materials, next-generation engines like the LEAP-1A and PW1100G have 15–20% higher fuel efficiency than earlier models like the CFM56 [20].

The CFM56, which was jointly developed by CFM International (a joint venture between GE Aviation and Safran), entered service in 1974 and became one of the best-selling turbofan engines in commercial aviation history, powering aircraft such as the Airbus A320ceo and Boeing 737 families. With a bypass ratio of 6:1, it established the performance benchmark for future single-aisle propulsion systems [24]. Its successor, the CFM LEAP engine, which began running for the first time in 2016, is a significant technology step forward, having a bypass ratio of nearly 11:1 and delivering around 15% lower fuel burn compared to the CFM56 [25]. It is enabled by technology advances such as composite fan blades, ceramic matrix composites in the hot section, and higher pressure ratios enabling more efficient thermodynamics. At the same time, the Pratt & Whitney PW1000G, which also entered service in 2016, features a geared turbofan (GTF) architecture in which a reduction gearbox allows the fan and low-pressure turbine to operate at their optimal speeds. This setup has a bypass ratio of almost 12:1 and has been demonstrated to be 16–20% more fuel efficient than the older CFM56-powered variants [26]. Collectively, these next-generation engines illustrate how new cycles, lightweight materials, and novel architectures are enabling the step-change improvements in efficiency and emissions required for sustainable aviation.

Circular economy approaches such as component reuse, remanufacturing, and materials recycling are gaining momentum. End-of-life recycling of aircraft components can reduce upstream emissions and material demand by up to 20% [27]. Additionally, initiatives like modular design are facilitating more efficient disassembly and recovery.

2.4. Chapter Summary

The fundamentals of life cycle assessment (LCA), aviation-specific environmental regulations, important conclusions from earlier LCA studies, and new climate mitigation techniques in the aviation industry were all covered in this chapter. Although a lot of research has been done to assess different phases of aircraft life cycles, there is still a lack of comprehensive, model-specific, and current cradle-to-grave life cycle assessments, especially for the popular Airbus A320. Current research frequently concentrates on discrete stages, like production or operations, without incorporating results into an all-encompassing sustainability evaluation. By providing a unified and interpretative LCA framework tailored to the A320 platform, this dissertation seeks to close that research gap.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The chapter explains how the research was carried out. It introduces the LCA framework from ISO 14040/44, sets the study boundaries, and describes the functional units chosen for analysis. It also outlines how data was gathered using the PRISMA approach and how the production, operation, and end-of-life phases of the aircraft were examined to understand their CO₂-eq environmental impacts.

All data in this dissertation are reported using standard SI/ISO units (e.g., g, kg, tonne, kN, MJ, GJ) to ensure clarity and consistency. The use of these internationally recognised units allows results to be easily compared with other studies and aligns the analysis with global research and reporting standards.

3.1. Research Design

This study employs a desk-based Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology and draws on secondary data from industry publications, peer-reviewed academic research, and publicly accessible databases (such as DEFRA, EcoInvent, and CCalC). Assessing the environmental impact of an Airbus A320 aircraft with various engine types (CFM56, LEAP-1A, and PW1100) is the main objective (see Section 1.3).

In order to preserve methodological precision, the literature review uses the PRISMA framework, which organises the search, screening, and selection of research relevant to life cycle analysis, aviation sustainability, and fuel emissions [28].

The research design adopts a cradle-to-grave system boundary, encompassing manufacturing, transportation, operational use (via a well-to-wake scope), and end-of-life recovery. This design is directly linked to the study objectives, which aim to quantify life cycle emissions of the Airbus A320, compare engine alternatives, and evaluate alignment with sustainability targets. To achieve these objectives, specific methods were employed.

- To estimate life cycle emissions is achieved by applying an LCA framework populated with data from prior research across various flight profiles.
- To compare the operational emissions of CFM56, LEAP-1A and PW1127G engines. This is conducted using well-to-wake emissions modelling, incorporating ICAO certified emission indices and fuel consumption data available from literature and regulatory databases [29].
- To link technological improvements to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is addressed through a qualitative mapping exercise aligned with SDG Targets.

3.2. Life Cycle Assessment

In accordance with international standards, this study will use a thorough Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach to measure and examine the environmental effects of the Airbus A320 over the period of its entire lifespan. Goal and Scope Definition, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) Analysis, Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), and Interpretation are the four interdependent phases (see Figure 3) that make up the International Organization for Standardization's (ISO) stringent standards for the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) process.

In this study, the four phases of LCA are applied to the Airbus A320. The goal and scope are to measure cradle-to-grave impacts over a 20-year lifetime and to compare efficiency per passenger-kilometre. The functional unit provides the reference point against which results are measured, and here two units are chosen. The first is one Airbus A320 over

its lifetime, which shows the total cradle-to-grave impact of a single aircraft. The second is one passenger-kilometre (pkm), which reflects the efficiency of carrying a passenger over distance. The lifetime unit highlights the overall burden, while the pkm unit allows comparisons across aircraft types and is consistent with industry and regulatory practice such as CORSIA and the EU ETS. The system boundary covers raw material extraction, manufacturing, operation (well-to-wake), and end-of-life. The inventory analysis compiles data on materials, fuel burn, flight hours and emissions from sources such as ICAO, Airbus and EcoInvent. In the impact assessment, these data are translated into indicators such as CO₂-equivalent and resource use. Finally, the interpretation identifies the dominant life cycle stages, acknowledges uncertainties, and highlights opportunities for improvement through advanced engines and sustainable fuels.

3.2.1. LCA System Boundaries and Scope

Figure 4 illustrates that the LCA considered in this dissertation consists of 3 phases. When conducting an LCA on a cradle-to-grave basis, it is necessary to grab a period from the raw materials to the end-of-life treatment. As can be seen in Figure 4, the phases include the manufacturing process, the active operational use period of the aircraft after the cradle-to-gate phase, and end-of-life treatment.

Figure 4 LCA Phases of A320 Aircraft

3.2.2. Phase 1: Manufacturing (Cradle-to-gate)

This phase includes every upstream process used in the manufacture of the aircraft, from the extraction of raw materials to the final step of assembly.

Based on the process-based LCA approach used by Kolios [18] and Spagnulo [21], the key components assessed include:

- Energy consumption in material processing and assembly lines.
- Logistics: Inter-facility transportation of fuselage, wings, engines, and subsystems across Airbus facilities in Europe.
- Material production: This study uses only secondary data available in published academic literature, reports and LCA databases (e.g., DEFRA, EcoInvent, CCalC). The material scope is limited to aircraft components for which emission and material inventory data are publicly available. The included materials are:
 - Aluminium alloys, CFRP, steel, and titanium for structural components
 - Jet-A1 fuel for operational emissions.

Materials excluded due to lack of publicly available data include textiles, cabin plastics, adhesives, paints, and in-flight entertainment systems. These components typically represent less than 1% of aircraft mass and are considered to have negligible impact on total life cycle emissions. The exclusion is justified based on data availability and methodological transparency.

3.2.3. Phase 2: Operational Usage

The operational phase represents the most GHG-intensive part of the aircraft's life cycle. This phase includes:

- Flight emissions during all typical operational stages: Landing Take-Off (LTO) cycle and Cruise.
- Engine options comparison between the CFM56 (A320ceo), LEAP-1A (A320neo) and PW1127G with the latter providing significant gains in fuel efficiency.

This study examines the effects of the engine options with three important engine options in the Airbus A320 series. With more than 33,000 delivered, the CFM56 is the best-selling commercial jet engine in the world, mainly powering the Boeing 737 and Airbus A320ceo aircraft [30]. LEAP-1A was introduced in 2016 with the A320neo, provides approximately 15% lower fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions compared to CFM56 equipped aircrafts [31]. Since it is so common, it is the natural basis for comparison.

Lewis [20] introduced a well-to-wake model considering three operational flight profiles (short-haul, medium-haul, long-haul), finding that short-haul routes produce disproportionately high emissions per passenger-kilometre (PAX-km) due to frequent take-off and landing cycles. In the context of Lewis's study, the flight profiles are categorised based on typical sector lengths, short-haul (0–1,500 km), medium-haul (1,500–4,000 km), and long-haul (above 4,000 km). Howe [17] similarly identified the operational stage as contributing over 70% of the total life cycle emissions of commercial passenger aircraft.

In this study, the operational phase is modelled to represent the lifetime of one Airbus A320 over 20 years. This corresponds to around 30,000 flights, 55,000 flight hours and about 45 million kilometres in total (see Table A1). On average each flight carries 147 passengers over a distance of 1,485 km. To reflect different patterns of use, flights are grouped into short-haul, medium-haul and long-haul, following Lewis [20]. These assumptions connect the analysis with the functional units of per aircraft and per passenger kilometre and provide a realistic picture of how emissions accumulate throughout the aircraft's service life.

3.2.4. Phase 3: End-of-Life (EoL)

The EoL phase covers the disassembly, recycling, and disposal of the aircraft and its materials. Although this stage contributes a smaller portion of total emissions, it plays a critical role in circularity and sustainability.

Spagnolo [21] highlighted that modular design and improved recycling strategies could enhance material recovery rates and reduce landfill dependency. In contrast, older models with lower recyclability ratios impose greater environmental costs post-retirement.

Based on methodologies presented by Cox [27], emissions savings from recycling are factored as environmental offsets against manufacturing burdens. The authors suggest that well-managed EoL strategies can reduce upstream material demand by up to 20%.

For the End-of-Life phase, the Airbus A320 was broken down into its main material groups: aluminium, CFRP composites, titanium, steel, and smaller fractions such as copper, plastics and wiring (see Table 10). The approach follows ISO 14040/44 and the avoided burden method, where recycled material is assumed to replace virgin production.

Each material was assigned a recycling rate based on industry averages and Aircraft Fleet Recycling Association (AFRA) guidelines. Aluminium and steel were treated as highly recyclable, titanium as moderately recyclable, and copper and other materials with partial recovery. CFRP, however, was given only a very small recovery rate, since fibre recycling technologies remain limited.

For every material, the model uses emission factors for both primary and secondary production from EcoInvent and literature. The difference between the two values shows the potential saving per kilogram when recycling is applied. This saving is then multiplied by the total mass of each material and its recycling rate to estimate its environmental credit.

In this way, the methodology captures both the benefits of materials like aluminium, which can be recovered efficiently, and the challenges posed by CFRP, which continues to be difficult to recycle. The process provides a structured way to include end-of-life treatment into the overall cradle-to-grave analysis of the aircraft.

Together, these three phases form the comprehensive structure of the cradle-to-grave LCA model adopted in this study. The segmentation facilitates better understanding of where mitigation strategies can be most effective in reducing the total carbon footprint of commercial aviation systems. In addition, evaluations will be made on the basis of reuse and circular economy, and alternative solutions will be presented in Chapter 5.

3.3. Data Collection Using the PRISMA Framework

The systematic literature review for this dissertation follows the PRISMA framework (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses), which provides a structured and transparent method for identifying, screening, and synthesizing relevant literature [32]. All stages of PRISMA Framework can be seen in Figure 5.

PRISMA is designed to improve the clarity, quality, and reproducibility of systematic reviews, especially where studies come from diverse disciplines such as environmental science, industrial engineering, and sustainable aviation. It ensures that the literature selection process is objective and minimizes bias through documented inclusion and exclusion criteria [28].

In this study, PRISMA was applied to gather and filter a wide body of literature related to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) in commercial aviation. This framework aligns with the aim of compiling cradle-to-grave GHG data and literature on the Airbus A320 by enabling a comprehensive and unbiased synthesis of existing findings.

The following databases were accessed to ensure coverage of both academic and grey literature:

- ScienceDirect

- Scopus
- Web of Science
- SpringerLink
- ICAO / EASA / Airbus / EU Commission / IATA Reports
- ResearchGate
- DMU Library
- Google Scholar

Examples of search strings include:

- "Life Cycle Assessment" and "Airbus A320"
- "Cradle-to-grave" and "aircraft emissions"
- "Sustainable aviation fuel" and "carbon footprint"
- "End-of-life aircraft recycling" and "narrow-body aircraft"

While researching the literature and data, a few criteria were set for inclusion. These are:

- Published between 2007–2025.
- Studies on aircraft LCA, sustainable aviation fuel, aircraft material lifecycle.
- Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, industry whitepapers and environmental reports, business reports.

Some of literature and data have been excluded due to:

- Non-aviation-related LCA studies.
- Wide-body aircraft analyses without relevance to narrow-body segment.
- Studies lacking transparent methodology or full-text access.

Figure 5 Flow of Information Through Different Phases PRISMA Framework [32]

Although PRISMA originated in medical sciences, its use in engineering and sustainability research is growing rapidly due to the increasing demand for transparency in systematic reviews involving multi-source datasets [32]. This approach was particularly suited for this dissertation, given the fragmented and multi-dimensional nature of LCA literature on the Airbus A320 platform.

The PRISMA framework-based literature selection procedure is depicted in the diagram in Figure 5. Through literature searches, 65 resources were found in the first pool. 42 full-text documents were evaluated for eligibility after duplicates were eliminated, and inclusion/exclusion criteria were applied. In the end, 20 studies which covered different LCA stages, technologies, and aircraft types relevant to the Airbus A320 were included into the final synthesis.

3.4. Data Analysis

This research adopts a quantitative desk-based approach, grounded entirely in secondary data extracted from peer-reviewed literature, official regulatory sources, and aviation industry reports (e.g. IATA, Airbus). Existing LCA results, fuel burn data [29], and emission indices are methodically collected from academic studies rather than using any private or raw databases.

In this study, all results were normalised to the functional unit of one Airbus A320 over a 20-year service life. This was modelled as around 32,220 flights, 55,000 flight hours and 45 million kilometres travelled (see Table A1). Data from different sources, such as fuel burn or emissions per flight or per hour, were scaled to this baseline so that everything referred to the same aircraft lifetime. In addition, values were also expressed per passenger-kilometre using an average capacity of 147 seats and an 80% load factor. This approach ensured that results could be compared consistently across engines, flight profiles and life cycle phases.

This literature-based methodology ensures transparency, traceability, and feasibility while enabling evidence-driven evaluation of current and emerging aircraft design strategies.

Chapter 4: Life Cycle Assessment

LCA requires collecting all environmentally significant flows associated with a product or activity. These consist of waste, energy, materials, emissions, and natural resources. Included are all flows associated with the manufacture, usage, and end-of-life phases of a product's life cycle. A product's life cycle environmental impacts are defined as the totality of these environmental flows.

The flow model for an A320 aircraft is shown in Figure 6. From the extraction of raw materials to the disposal of end-of-life materials, it describes the life cycle steps in order, with matching inputs (materials, energy, and transportation) and outputs (waste and emissions) at each stage. This is a classical LCI representation, focusing on quantifying elementary flows in and out of the techno sphere for each subsystem.

Figure 6 Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) Diagram

A systematic LCI framework for the Airbus A320, consisting of three different phases. Manufacturing, usage, and decommissioning. This system boundary technique has been used regularly in several LCA studies, including Lopes [33], Cox [27], and Howe [17]. It is in accordance with ISO 14040/14044 standards [12].

The CCalC2 LCA tool and its embedded datasets with the EcoInvent (v2.2)[34] database were used to calculate quantitative inputs and outputs for background life cycle inventories. In addition, at the points where the datasets were insufficient, the most up-to-date and consistent data were preferred by making use of the literature and publications. By preferring articles that clearly provide unitary data, especially in Phase 1 calculation, it is aimed to calculate the unit constants (kgCO_2 , MJ) in the most up-to-date and consistent way by making a comparative article search. Although the basic functional unit (f.u) during LCA was based on 1 Aircraft, it was evaluated as Passenger-km (PAX-km) for comparison in the operational phase. In addition, the calculations were mass-based. Although process-based LCAs are more consistent and detailed, mass-based analysis, which is more accepted, has been performed due to both the lack of publicly available data and limited resources about changing and developing technologies.

4.1. Phase 1: Aircraft Production (Cradle-to-Gate)

During Phase 1, raw materials are extracted, intermediate processing is carried out, and final components are manufactured. Materials such as aluminium, CFRP, steel, and

titanium are primary contributors to this stage. All composite materials in the A320 are treated as carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP). This is because CFRP makes up the majority of composites used in modern narrow-body aircraft, and reliable life cycle data for other composites is limited. For consistency, the 15% share of composites in the aircraft mass was therefore modelled entirely as CFRP.

The Operational Empty Weight (OEW) of an functional unit, i.e. Airbus A320 aircraft, is considered to be 42,400 kg with CMF-56 engines including the weight of the structure, power plant, furnishing, systems and all other operators' items such as life vests and engine oil [35]. During the calculations, energy and environmental use, CO₂-eq emissions were calculated, European Union border conditions and the location of Airbus' finishing factory in Toulouse, France, were taken into account. At the points where the accuracy of the data provided in the datasets could not be ensured, references were taken from previous research.

The aircraft's lifespan is taken account of 20 years; this is a conservative assumption because aircraft parts, including frames, may be more resilient. Capital goods used in production are not included in the second-order LCA model. Large commercial aeroplanes typically have millions of parts and components and modelling all of these is simply not feasible [17]. Therefore, the A320 has been separated into six major structural components that can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Component Breakdown of A320 [17]

Previous studies have encountered difficulties in determining the proportional contribution of individual aircraft components to the total Operating Empty Weight (OEW), with notable differences between reported values. However, research by Howe [17] and Spagnulo [21] presents closely aligned component weight distributions, suggesting that their results are representative of the actual structural mass distribution of the Airbus A320. To ensure the use of current and reliable information, this study selected the dataset from the more recent source, taking into account potential changes in materials and manufacturing methods over time.

Component percentages from Lewis [20] and Spagnulo [21] were normalised to match the OEW baseline of 42.4 t as reported by Kumar [35]. For example, the wings account for 27% of the OEW, equivalent to 11.4 t/f.u. This approach integrates up-to-date, corroborated literature with a validated reference mass, reducing uncertainty in the weight distribution and providing a robust foundation for subsequent Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) calculations.

Table 2 shows the results of the main components of the aircraft in terms of mass (t/f.u) and percentage. Although the material density used in the main elements varies according to the type, it was evaluated cumulatively because there is not enough data in the literature that clearly addresses this issue.

Components	Mass %	Mass (t/f.u)
Wings (2x)	27	11.4
Fuselage	19	8.1
CFM56 (2x)	20	8.5
Main Landing Gear	4	1.7
Horizontal Stabilizer	11	4.7
Vertical Stabilizer	6	2.5
Other	13	5.5
	Total	42.4

Table 2 A320 Structural Components and Mass Distribution of the Airbus A320 [20], [21], [35]

Internal components and onboard systems were not included in the analysis, which is an unavoidable drawback of this study. For these components, such as flight deck instrumentation, hydraulic systems, and batteries, accurate mass and material composition statistics are challenging for researchers to come through because they are frequently produced by third-party suppliers and are not completely revealed in publicly accessible technical literature. Due to this absence, the total component weight distribution and the ensuing environmental impact estimations are rather imprecise.

The wings are the most important component, representing 27% (11.4 tons), which highlights the high structural demand required for providing lift, fuel, and load-carrying capacity. The fuselage, at 19% (8.1 tons) weight, is the main structure intended for passenger and cargo accommodation, shaped for aerodynamic excellence and pressurization. Propulsion components, best exemplified by the CFM56 model representing two engines, make up 20% (8.5 tons) in total weight, a sizeable figure considering the propulsion components are at the same time large in weight and technologically complex, employing high-strength alloy parts and carefully designed components. Each CFM56-5B engine, for example, has a base dry weight of 2380 kg, not including the weight of oil and fuel [17].

The main landing gear weighs 4% (1.7 ton), which is relatively light, but it must handle repeated high-impact loads. The horizontal stabiliser (11%, 4.7 ton) and vertical stabiliser (6%, 2.5 ton) together create the empennage. This part is crucial for providing aerodynamic stability and control. The other category (13%, 5.5 ton) includes various structural elements that are not detailed individually, such as fairings, doors, and non-primary load-bearing assemblies.

From an LCA perspective, this distribution matters because the mass of each component directly affects the total material needs and the emissions generated during manufacturing. For instance, large elements like the wings and fuselage consume most of the

materials, often using aluminium alloys or composites that have a high embodied energy. On the other hand, lighter parts like the landing gear, while making up a smaller share of the OEW, may have a bigger environmental impact because they use resource-heavy materials like titanium and high-strength steels.

4.1.1. Raw Material Extraction and Intermediate Process Stage

Raw Material	Mass (%)	Mass (t/f.u)	Energy (GJ/t)	Energy (GJ/f.u)	Emission Factor (tCO ₂ -eq/t)	Total Emission (tCO ₂ -eq/f.u)
Aluminium	68	28.8	218	6278.4	18.9	544.32
Composites (CFRP)	15	6.40	286	1830.4	8.5	54.4
Titanium	6	2.55	553	1410.15	4.6	11.6535
Steel	9	3.81	32	121.92	0.42	1.61925
Miscellaneous	2	0.85	72	61.2	4.2	3.553
<i>Energy-based</i>						249
Total		42.4		9702.07		864.54575

Table 3 Airbus A320 Structural Raw Material Extraction and Component Production Energy Consumptions and CO₂-eq Emissions [17], [21], [34], [35], [36]

A comprehensive review of the Airbus A320 structure's raw material composition, energy consumption, and CO₂-equivalent emissions during the extraction and intermediate processing stages is provided in Table 3. The total aircraft structural mass considered in this analysis is 42.4 ton, with aluminium dominating at 68% of the total mass. The energy intensities (GJ per tonne) and CO₂-eq emission values for aluminium, CFRP, titanium, steel and other materials were obtained from CCaLC and EcoInvent v2.2 databases [34]. These cradle-to-gate values were then projected onto the A320's operating empty weight (OEW) to estimate the total energy demand and CO₂-eq emissions shown in Table 3.

As it can be seen in Table 3, aluminium makes up 28.8 tons of the structure and produces 544.32 tCO₂-eq, or more than 63% of the total emissions from raw materials, because of its high emission factor (18.9 tCO₂/ton). Despite its favourable strength-to-weight ratio for aerospace applications, aluminium's energy-intensive primary production process is reflected in this significant contribution.

CFRP comprise 15% of the mass but require 286 GJ/ton, a higher energy intensity than aluminium. This results in 1830.4 GJ of embodied energy. Nevertheless, due to a lower emission factor as 8.5 tCO₂/ton, CFRP's total emissions are 54.4 tCO₂-eq, substantially lower than aluminium's, demonstrating that the carbon intensity of the energy source is as important as the total energy consumed [35].

In Table 3, despite making up only 6% of the structure's mass, titanium emits 11.65 tCO₂-eq due to its high energy intensity (553 GJ/ton) and emission factor (4.6 tCO₂/ton). The energy-intensive refining process, which is common for aerospace-grade titanium alloys, is the main cause of the high environmental burden per kilogram. Steel and other various materials, on the other hand, have relatively low energy intensities and emission factors and collectively account for around 11% of the overall mass. Their combined 5.17 tCO₂-eq. contribution to the total GWP is small.

The embodied energy of all raw materials amounts to 9702 GJ, resulting in 864.6 tCO₂-eq. In addition, 249 tCO₂-eq was added to account for electricity used in processing and manufacturing, based on the French grid mix since final assembly takes place in France. This covers direct electricity use only and avoids double counting. Although this assumption keeps the analysis consistent, it adds uncertainty because A320 components are produced in different countries with varying grid intensities.

4.1.2. Assembly Stage

In this study, the assembly stage was modelled using data from Kumar [35] rather than process-level estimates for each component. These values were scaled to the A320's material mass distribution to calculate energy use and emissions per tonne. This ensures that assembly energy reflects the aircraft's overall structure, while also keeping results consistent with other LCA phases. The outcomes are broadly in line with the relative values reported by Spagnuolo [21], which supports the validity of this approach.

Raw Material	Mass (t/f.u)	Embodied Energy in Aircraft Manufacturing (GJ/t)	Embodied Energy in Aircraft Manufacturing (GJ/f.u)	Emissions (tCO ₂ -eq/t)	Emissions (tCO ₂ -eq/f.u)
Aluminium	28.8	218	6278.4	1.28	36.8
Composites (CFRP)	6.40	287	1836.8	6.04	38.7
Titanium	2.55	553	1410.15	31.55	80.5
Steel	3.81	32	121.92	2.89	11.0
Miscellaneous	0.85	72	61.2	4.18	3.6
<i>Energy-based</i>					249
Total			9708.47		419.6

Table 4 A320 Assembly Consumptions and Emissions by Raw Material [17], [18], [21], [35]

Table 4 shows the CO₂-equivalent emissions and energy consumption of the Airbus A320 by raw material type during the assembly process. Aircraft manufacture uses a total of 9708.47 GJ of embodied energy, resulting in 419.6 tCO₂-eq of emissions.

Aluminium contributes 36.8 tCO₂-eq and has a relatively low emission factor of 1.28 tCO₂/ton, despite its enormous mass of 28.8 t. Although having lesser mass, composites (CFRP) contribute slightly more with 38.7 tCO₂-eq because of their greater embodied energy (287 GJ/ton) and moderate emission intensity. Despite only weighing 2.55 t, titanium has the greatest single-material GWP (80.5 tCO₂-eq) due to its extremely high emission factor (31.55 tCO₂/ton). Steel and other materials contribute little overall because of their low energy intensity and low mass.

From the perspective of an LCA standpoint, the findings show that CFRP and titanium have significant effect per unit mass during the assembly phase, but aluminium dominates energy consumption because of its volume, although having a relatively low emission when compared with others. This implies that buying from low-carbon production facilities or making targeted material substitutions could have a major positive environmental impact.

4.1.3. Transportation

Conventional aircraft production involves a complicated overseas supply network that transports significant amounts of components and raw materials over long distances. Although the operational phase dominates an aircraft's lifetime emissions, the upstream stages still contribute to the manufacturing carbon footprint. Transporting components and materials "throughout the value chain" can actually result in significant emissions prior to final assembly.

As mentioned before, the A320's components are assembled at various locations before they are sent to Toulouse's FAL. Manufacturing facilities are spread across many countries and different forms of transportation are in use. From raw material extraction to final assembly, the transportation of each sub-assembly has been taken into account by previous researches. Due to the scarcity of publicly available transportation data, this research draws on previous estimations reported in Howe's [17] study. It is predicted that approximately $1.67 \times 10^4 \text{ t.km}$ of air freight and $1.37 \times 10^4 \text{ t.km}$ of road transport are required to relocate all major assemblies and sub-assemblies to the FAL in Toulouse (see Table A4) [17], [18]. As a result of the LCA made in the light of these data, Phase 1 GHG emission from transportation was determined as 11.39 tCO₂-eq for functional unit (1-unit A320).

4.1.4. Cradle-to-Gate Results

Figure 8 Comparative CO₂-eq Emissions of Raw Material Process & Assembly

The comparative bar chart on Figure 8 illustrates the CO₂-equivalent emissions for both raw material processing and assembly phases of the Airbus A320. Aluminium stands out as the largest single contributor in the raw material stage with 544.32 tCO₂-eq, while titanium has the highest assembly-phase contribution 80.5 tCO₂-eq despite its relatively low mass. Energy-related emissions are also significant in both phases (249 tCO₂-eq each), reflecting electricity consumption during processing and assembly. CFRP's contributions are balanced between stages (54.54 vs. 38.7 tCO₂-eq), while steel and miscellaneous materials have minimal overall impact. Used data and assumptions for water consumption, transportation and CFRP are demonstrated in Table A3, Table A4 and Table A5 in Appendices section.

Figure 9 Total Emissions for Phase 1 Except Transportation by Material

Figure 9 sums total emissions by materials of raw material and assembly stages, showing aluminium at 45% of the total, followed by energy at 39%, with titanium and CFRP each at 7%. Steel and miscellaneous materials combined contribute only about 2%. This confirms that reducing aluminium-related emissions and decarbonising electricity supply could deliver the largest overall GWP reductions.

Figure 10 Cradle-to-Gate Emission Proportions

Figure 10, clearly shows the emission distribution tCO₂-eq emissions in the A320 production process. Obviously, emissions from pre-assembly processes account for the largest share at 67%. Then, while the final assembly and operations were carried out before operational use at the FAL factory, it is striking that 419.6 tCO₂-eq emissions emerged, affecting cradle-to-gate emissions with a weight of 32%. The environmental cost of transportation used during the supply chain is only 1% with 11.39 tCO₂-eq. In particular, it is clear that air cargo modal plays a dominant role in the total transportation footprint due to the fact that the emission coefficient per t.km is much higher, although the total t.km value is only slightly higher compared to land transportation. In the literature [17], [18] confirm this situation, emphasizing that emissions from logistics can be reduced by 60–80% if multimodal transport (rail and shipping) is used instead of air cargo.

The amount of CO₂-eq emissions for phase 1 scope is 1295.5 tCO₂-eq/f.u., according to the estimations above. Nonetheless, It is important to note that the most accurate and optimistic assumptions were used in the computations and assessed for France and the

European Union. More accurate and realistic assumptions could come off as more negative results.

4.2. Phase 2: Operational Phase

Aviation is a significant contributor to environmental impacts, not only from fuel combustion (CO₂ and other exhaust gases) but also from Maintenance Repair and Operations (MRO) and fuel production. To fully understand an aircraft’s environmental footprint, a life cycle assessment (LCA) is used, considering all stages from fuel production (well) to combustion (wake) and including maintenance operations. In this report, the selected functional unit considers 20 years operational life of an Airbus A320 aircraft (45 million km of travel) carrying ~147 passengers on average (about 81.5% load factor).

4.2.1. Tank-to-Wake (TTW)

Tank-to-Wake (TTW) emissions refer to the greenhouse gas output generated directly during the combustion of fuel. In aviation, TTW covers the emissions primarily in the form of carbon dioxide (CO₂) released into the atmosphere when the chemical energy of the fuel is converted into mechanical energy within the aircraft engine. This stage is assessed independently from upstream processes such as fuel extraction, transportation and storage, focusing solely on the combustion phase.

Especially today, more environmentally friendly engines and fuels are preferred in the field of aviation. The amount of GHG emitted by three different engines in use in A320ceo and A320neo aircraft due to operation under the same conditions and life-span will be shown. Each engine’s performance and emissions profile differ due to technological advancements (e.g. higher bypass ratios and advanced combustors), which in turn influence the LCA results.

The A320's life cycle GHG footprint is dominated by the operational usage phase because manufacturing and EoL emissions are greatly outweighed by fuel burn throughout the course of 20 years of service. The ICAO Engine Emissions Databank [29] fuel flow/emission index data and a standard flight profile (ICAO LTO cycle & cruise [37] are used to quantify the overall fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions of an A320 over its lifetime.

Table 5 summarizes the results for three engine configurations. The baseline is A320ceo with CFM56-5B5/3 engines, and the A320neo with either LEAP-1A26/26E1 or PW1127G-JM engines per flight on average. The functional unit is taken as both total emissions per aircraft lifetime and normalized emissions per passenger-kilometre (kgCO₂-eq/pkm) for comparability.

Engine Configuration	Fuel Use (t)	CO ₂ Emitted (t)	Emissions per pkm (kgCO ₂ -eq)
A320ceo CFM56-5B5/3 (Jet-A1)	122,500	387,047	0.0586
A320neo LEAP-1A26/26E1 (Jet-A1)	109,300	345,406	0.0523
A320neo PW1127G-JM (Jet-A1)	99,500	313,930	0.0475

Table 5 TTW Phase Emissions Results by Engines

CO₂-equivalent (CO₂-eq) emissions for every engine type and flight phase are calculated in this study using the measured or modelled fuel mass burnt. The generic formula is used to convert fuel mass to CO₂-eq mass:

$$CO_2eq(t) = Fuel\ Mass(t) \times Emission\ Factor\left(\frac{t\ CO_2}{t\ Fuel}\right)$$

The emission factor utilized in this analysis for Jet-A1 aviation fuel is 3.16 tCO₂ per ton of fuel consumed. According to the IPCC's definition and the ICAO environmental modelling guidelines, this factor is based on Jet-A1's carbon content and the molecular weight ratio of CO₂ to carbon [37]. Although they are also by-products of combustion, hydrocarbons (HC), carbon monoxide (CO), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) contribute very little to the total CO₂-equivalent value when compared to the CO₂ generated from fuel oxidation. The combined global warming potential of HC, CO, and NO_x emissions, for example, usually amounts to less than 1% of the CO₂-equivalent value resulting from fuel consumption in traditional kerosene-powered aircraft, according to ICAO and IPCC research.

The CO₂-eq calculation in this study did not include these species due to their low proportional impact and to preserve methodological simplicity. Fuel-derived CO₂, which accounts for the majority of operating greenhouse gas emissions from jet aircraft, continued to be the main emphasis.

The baseline A320ceo configuration, equipped with CFM56-5B5/3 engines, is estimated to consume approximately 1.225×10^5 tonnes of Jet-A1 fuel over its 20-year operational lifespan, corresponding to 3.87×10^5 tCO₂-eq. Under the stated assumptions, this equates to roughly 0.0586 kgCO₂ per passenger-kilometre (pkm).

Replacing the CFM56 engines with more efficient LEAP-1A26/26E1 turbofans, as in the A320neo, reduces lifetime fuel consumption to 1.093×10^5 t (3.454×10^5 tCO₂-eq), representing an approximate 11% reduction in operational greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions relative to the baseline.

An even greater improvement is observed with the PW1127G-JM geared turbofan, which consumes 0.995×10^5 t of fuel (3.139×10^5 tCO₂-eq) over the same period, achieving about 18% lower operational GHG emissions compared with the CFM56 configuration. This corresponds to 0.0475 kgCO₂/pkm, versus 0.0586 kg CO₂/pkm for the baseline.

These results align with the anticipated performance enhancements of the A320neo program, wherein next-generation engines like the LEAP-1A and PW1100G generally yield fuel efficiency gains of 15–20% above the CFM56 series. Although the smaller-than-stated reduction for the LEAP-1A in this model (11% vs. 15% claimed) may be explained by real-world operational factors (such as route structure, average flight length, and engine power settings), both new engine types clearly outperform the legacy CFM56 in terms of fuel consumption and related CO₂ emissions. Detailed phase-by-phase results for the three engine configurations are presented in Table 6.

Phase	Fuel (t)	CO2-eq (t)
CFM56-5B5 Total	122,483.11	387,046.63
CFM56 Taxi (2x)	8,674.35	27,410.94
CFM56 Take-Off	2,269.40	7,171.31
CM56 Climb	5,927.71	18,731.57
CFM56 Cruise	94,833.99	299,675.40
CFM56 Approach	10,777.66	34,057.41
LEAP-1A26/26E1 Total	109,305.86	345,406.52
LEAP-1A Taxi (2x)	8,580.06	27,113.00
LEAP-1A Take-Off	2,185.63	6,906.59
LEAP-1A Climb	5,664.44	17,899.62
LEAP-1A Cruise	89,336.36	282,302.91
LEAP-1A Approach	3,539.37	11,184.40
PW1127G-JM Total	99,345.23	313,930.92
PW1127G Taxi (2x)	7,542.91	23,835.60
PW1127G Take-Off	2,030.78	6,417.28
PW1127G Climb	5,345.31	16,891.19
PW1127G Cruise	81,089.93	256,244.18
PW1127G Approach	3,336.29	10,542.67

Table 6 Jet-1A Tank-to-Wake (TTW) Detailed Results by Engines

4.2.2. LTO vs. Cruise Emissions

Fuel flow data were segmented into standard operational phases to assess emissions during the Landing/Take-Off (LTO) cycle versus cruise. A complete flight cycle, including taxi, take-off, climb and approach, consumes approximately 600 to 680 kg of fuel for the A320 (two engines combined). For example, the CFM56-5B5/3 (2 unit) burns about 686 kg per LTO cycle, whereas the PW1127G-JM requires only 606 kg under identical conditions, representing a 12% reduction due to its higher bypass ratio and more efficient thermodynamic cycle. The LEAP-1A26/26E1 lies between these two, at 660 kg per LTO cycle, a 4% reduction compared with the CFM56 baseline.

These reductions in high-thrust phases translate directly into proportionally lower CO₂ emissions for the A320neo engines during take-off and climb. However, over the aircraft's lifetime operational distance, cruise fuel burn accounts for the majority of total emissions. In this study, cruise represented approximately 80% of total fuel consumption, for instance 9.48×10^4 t for the CFM56 configuration..

The detailed calculation results and inputs are presented in Table 6, Table A2 and Table A6 in the appendices. While the original data sources are explicitly presented and cited, reasonable engineering assumptions were applied in cases where complete datasets were unavailable.

4.2.3. Analysis of TTW Phase

Table 7 presents operational phase emissions and fuel use for three A320 engine configurations. The totals at the bottom of each engine section are consistent with the phase-by-phase sums for HC (Hydrocarbons), CO (Carbon Monoxide), NO_x (Nitrogen Oxides), and fuel consumption. The distribution of thrust percentages and thrust (kN) aligns with ICAO Landing and Take-Off (LTO) cycle definitions and cruise profiles.

Engine	Data	HC (t)	CO(t)	NOx(t)	THRUST (%)	THRUST (kN)	FUEL (t)
CFM56-5B5/3	Taxi (2x)	30.79	362.33	33.05	7.00	13.71	8,674.35
	Take-Off	0.07	0.34	37.26	100.00	195.80	2,269.40
	Climb	0.18	1.19	83.05	85.00	166.43	5,927.71
	Cruise	28.45	94.83	1,138.01	25.00	48.95	94,833.99
	Approach	0.47	29.28	47.60	30.00	58.74	10,777.66
	Total	59.96	487.97	1,338.97	-	-	122,483.11
LEAP-1A26/26E1	Taxi (2x)	2.49	185.59	39.55	7.00	16.88	8,580.06
	Take-Off	0.04	0.52	67.32	100.00	241.20	2,185.63
	Climb	0.11	1.47	75.79	85.00	205.02	5,664.44
	Cruise	22.33	71.47	848.70	25.00	60.30	89,336.36
	Approach	0.14	9.38	30.97	30.00	72.36	3,539.37
	Total	25.12	268.43	1,062.33	-	-	109,305.86
PW1127G-JM	Taxi (2x)	3.47	185.03	39.22	7.00	16.86	7,542.91
	Take-Off	0.14	0.55	42.26	100.00	240.88	2,030.78
	Climb	0.37	1.92	90.60	85.00	102.37	5,345.31
	Cruise	16.22	56.76	689.26	25.00	120.44	81,089.93
	Approach	0.20	16.31	35.33	30.00	72.26	3,336.29
	Total	20.40	260.58	896.68	-	-	99,345.23

Table 7 LTO & Cruise Phase Lifetime GHG Emissions Results

For LTO modes (idle/taxi, take-off, climb-out, approach) the ICAO sheets give emission indices in g pollutant per kg fuel (g/kg) and fuel flow in kg/s (with mode times). These quantitative details are given in Table A1 and Table A2 in appendix section. It is taken into account that the aircraft has 2 engines. Since GHG production depends on the amount of fuel consumption, there is no multiplier effect, but since fuel consumption is given per unit engine in ICAO (2025) data, the double value is taken into account.

For any LTO or Cruise mod, results are calculated by the equation:

$$GHG\ Mass\ (t) = \frac{(Fuel_{mode}[kg]) \times (El[g/kg])}{10^6}$$

- El: Emission Factor by mode (see Table A2).

In terms of lifetime fuel consumption, the baseline CFM56-5B5/3 engine configuration uses 122,483 tonnes of Jet-A1 over 20 years of operation. The LEAP-1A26/26E1 reduces this to 109,306 tonnes, which is a 10% decrease compared with the baseline. The PW1127G-JM achieves the lowest total at 99,345 tonnes, representing a 18.9% reduction. Across all three engine types, the cruise phase is the dominant contributor to total fuel consumption, accounting for 78% for the CFM56, 81% for the LEAP-1A, and 82% for the PW1127G.

For the taxi and take-off phases combined, the CFM56-5B5/3 consumes 8,674.35 tonnes during taxi and 2,269.40 tonnes during take-off, for a total of 10,943.75 tonnes. The LEAP-1A burns 8,580.06 tonnes in taxi and 2,185.63 tonnes in take-off, totalling 10,765.69 tonnes (a 1.63% reduction). The PW1127G-JM records 7,542.91 tonnes for taxi and 2,030.78 tonnes for take-off, totalling 9,573.69 tonnes, which is 12.50% lower than the CFM56 baseline.

During climb, the CFM56 consumes 5,927.71 tonnes, the LEAP-1A 5,664.44 tonnes (a 4.45% reduction), and the PW1127G 5,345.31 tonnes (a 9.82% reduction). This indicates that the PW engine delivers greater fuel efficiency during high-power climb operations.

Certain aspects of engine design are associated with these performance improvements. With composite fan blades, a high bypass ratio of 11.10, and enhanced aerodynamic efficiency, the LEAP-1A has a lower specific fuel consumption (SFC) than the CFM56, which has a bypass ratio of 6.00. The geared turbofan architecture of the PW1127G-JM decouples the fan from the low-pressure turbine, enabling both to run at their ideal rotational speeds and increasing efficiency during all flight phases.

In conclusion, compared to the CFM56 baseline, the LEAP-1A and PW1127G both produce measurable decreases in lifetime fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions. While the PW1127G demonstrates the most noteworthy advantages, especially in the cruise and high-thrust phases, the LEAP-1A produces moderate savings throughout all phases, which is in line with the A320neo program's efficiency goals.

In Figure 11, visualized in a comparative format the total GHG emissions for each engine type for better demonstrating.

Figure 11 Comparative TTW GHG Emissions of A320 Lifetime

4.2.4. Well-to-Tank (WTT)

WTT emissions account for the upstream processes before fuel combustion. These include the energy requirements of oil extraction, refinery processing, and the logistics of moving fuel to airports. According to the UK Government’s Greenhouse Gas Reporting Conversion Factors 2025 dataset [38] the WTT emission factor for aviation turbine fuel is 661.79468 kgCO₂eq/t fuel.

$$WTT\ CO_2eq\ (t) = Fuel\ Mass\ (t) \times 0.66179468 \left(\frac{t\ CO_2}{t\ Fuel} \right)$$

The total WTT emissions for each engine types for 2 unit, calculated using the DEFRA 2025 factor of 0.66179468 tCO₂ per tonne of fuel, are shown in Table 8.

Engine	Fuel Mass (t)	WTT CO ₂ -eq (t)
CFM56-5B5/3	122,483.11	81,058.67
LEAP-1A26/26E1	109,305.86	72,338.04
PW1127G-JM	99,345.23	65,746.14

Table 8 WTT CO₂-eq Emissions

The CFM56-5B5 records the highest WTT emissions due to its greater lifetime fuel consumption. LEAP-1A26 shows a reduction of approximately 11% compared to the CFM56-5B5, while the PW1127G-JM exhibits a reduction of approximately 19%, indicating improved fuel efficiency in newer engine designs.

When expressed as a proportion of total Well-to-Wake (WTW) emissions, WTT contributes between 17% across all three engines. This consistent percentage reflects the fixed fuel-based WTT factor in DEFRA's dataset, making the absolute values proportional to total fuel burn.

4.2.5. Well-to-Wake (WTW)

Well-to-Wake (WTW) is a life-cycle assessment (LCA) approach that measures the total amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the extraction of a fuel to its final combustion during consumption. The WTW profile for Jet A-1 aviation turbine fuel is made up of two primary parts:

- Well-to-Tank (WTT): Upstream emissions from resource extraction, crude oil transport, refining into Jet A-1, storage, and delivery to the aircraft.
- Tank-to-Wake (TTW): Direct emissions generated during the combustion of the fuel in aircraft engines during flight.

$$WTT + TTW = WTW$$

The sum of these two components represents the full WTW emissions of the fuel.

In section 4.2.1, TTW consumptions and GHG impacts are explained widely.

Direct emissions from fuel combustion (TTW), fuel supply chain emissions (WTT), and the total Well-to-Wake values for the three engine alternatives taken into consideration in this study are compared in Table 9.

The comparative WTT, TTW, and WTW CO₂-equivalent emissions for three distinct engine options introduced on the Airbus A320 family are shown in Table 9. With 387,047 tCO₂-eq (TTW), 81,059 tCO₂-eq (WTT), and 468,105 tCO₂-eq (WTW), the baseline configuration, the CFM56-5B5/3, has the highest lifetime emissions.

In contrast, the LEAP-1A26/26E1 and PW1127G-JM engines show substantial improvements in both operational and upstream emissions. The LEAP-1A reduces WTW emissions to 417,745 tCO₂-eq, corresponding to a 11% decrease relative to the CFM56, while the PW1127G achieves the most significant reduction with 379,677 tCO₂-eq, amounting to a 18.9% improvement compared to the baseline.

Engine	WTT CO ₂ -eq (t)	TTW CO ₂ -eq (t)	WTW CO ₂ -eq (t)
CFM56-5B5/3	81,058.67	387,046.63	468,105.3
LEAP-1A26/26E1	72,338.04	345,406.52	417,744.56
PW1127G-JM	65,746.14	313,930.92	379,677.06

Table 9 WTW CO₂-eq Emissions of A320 Lifetime by Engine Options

The proportional decreases in TTW and WTT are the same because constant emission factors were used in both computations. This result is anticipated because, like direct combustion emissions, upstream emissions scale linearly with fuel consumption. The WTT, TTW, and WTW of the LEAP-1A26/26E1 are reduced by about 11% in comparison to the CFM56-5B5/3 baseline, whereas the PW1127G-JM is reduced by almost 19%. The WTW footprint's relative distribution is unchanged in spite of these decreases, with direct combustion during flight (TTW) making up 83% of total emissions and upstream processes (WTT) contributing roughly 17%. This suggests that while supply chain emissions are not negligible, the most immediate and significant reductions in aviation's carbon footprint come from efficiency enhancements that lower in-flight fuel consumption. In conclusion, the table illustrates three main aspects;

- The PW1127G-JM provides the greatest overall reduction with nearly 18% lower WTW emissions.
- The LEAP-1A offers a moderate but consistent improvement of about 11%.
- Even though TTW accounts for the majority of emissions, advancements in engine technology continue to be the principal means of achieving near-term decarbonisation; nevertheless, more extensive long-term reductions must also take upstream emissions into account within a whole life cycle framework.

4.2.6. Maintenance, Repair and Operations (MRO)

The aviation sector is facing increasing request to measure greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from all sources. The focus currently is on in-flight fuel economy. But life cycle assessments (LCAs) should also account for indirect emissions from aeroplane maintenance. Over the course of an Airbus A320's 20-year service life, this study calculates the greenhouse gas emissions produced by maintenance procedures.

It is anticipated that the Airbus A320 will remain in service for 20 years. The estimated number of flights per year is 1,511, with an average duration of 108 minutes. The aircraft is anticipated to complete 30,220 flights, accrue ~55,000 flying hours, and cover ~45 million km over its lifetime.

The maintenance phase of a commercial aircraft such as the Airbus A320 represents an important contributor to its overall life cycle environmental impact. The primary source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is still the combustion of operating fuel, but maintenance operations also play a part. Production of spare parts, component replacement, lubrication, inspections, and waste management are some of these tasks. Over the course of the aircraft's service life, they all add to the energy and material consumption.

Depending on the engine type and airline operating environment, maintenance costs for the A320 family are generally projected to be between \$1,000 and \$2,000 USD per flying

hour [35]. In terms of the environment these expenses related to the consumption of resources, the production of replacement parts, energy consumption in workshops, and the handling of replaced components at the end of their useful lives [39].

The life cycle maintenance emissions of an Airbus A320 were estimated by examining key categories of routine and scheduled maintenance that occur throughout the aircraft's operational life. The study focuses on activities that have measurable energy consumption, material use, and associated indirect emissions.

The primary maintenance activities considered are as follows:

- Routine line and base checks, including A-checks and C-checks
- Engine overhauls
- Replacement of consumables such as filters and fluids
- Transport of parts and materials
- Energy used in maintenance hangars

All of these processes require metals, composites, lubricants, and energy, and they generate waste that must be recycled or managed.

The environmental impact of planned maintenance activities was measured over the course of the Airbus A320 family's 25-year operational lifespan in a thorough life cycle assessment study. The reference scenario, representing a full-service network carrier (FSNC) operating primarily short-haul flights, revealed that the total GHG attributable solely to maintenance activities amounted to 1,555 tonnes of CO₂-equivalent (tCO₂-eq). Furthermore, when normalized by total flight hours over the service life, the study reported an average emission intensity of 28.3 kg of CO₂-equivalent per flight hour (kgCO₂-eq/FH). These findings emphasize the value of considering MRO activities in aviation-related sustainability assessments and draw attention to the non-negligible but frequently disregarded environmental burden associated with aircraft maintenance [39].

In our case, the service life is not 25 years, and the values will differ. Below are the results and formula;

The total number of flights over the aircraft's lifetime is calculated by multiplying the average annual flight frequency by the total service years.

$$\textit{Total Flights (TF)} = \textit{Flights per Year} \times \textit{Service Year}$$

$$TF = 1511 \times 20 = 30,220$$

Given an annual flight frequency of 1,511 flights and a 20-year service period, the aircraft is expected to complete 30,220 flights in total.

Total block hours are estimated by multiplying the average flight block time by the total number of flights.

$$\textit{Total Hours (TH)} = \textit{Block Time(hours)} \times \textit{TF}$$

$$TH = 1.8 \times 30,220 \cong 54,396 \textit{ Flight Hours (FH)}$$

Assuming an average block time of 1.8 hours per flight, the total operational time amounts to approximately 54,396 flight hours (FH) across the entire fleet lifetime.

The cumulative maintenance-related emissions are calculated by multiplying the emission intensity per flight hour by the total flight hours.

$$\text{Lifetime Maintenance Emission (LME)} = \text{Reference Factor} \times \text{FH}$$

$$\text{LME} = \frac{28.3 \text{ kgCO}_2 \text{ eq}}{\text{FH}} \times 54,396(\text{FH}) = 1,539.4 \text{ tCO}_2 \text{ eq/fu}$$

Using the reference intensity of 28.3 kgCO₂-eq per flight hour, the total lifetime maintenance emissions are estimated to be 1,539.4 tonnes of CO₂-equivalent per functional unit (A320). Notably, the lifetime maintenance emissions calculated in this analysis using operating parameters closely match the 1,555 tCO₂-eq over 25 years number stated in the Rahn's study [39] reference scenario. This consistency validates the accuracy of the underlying flight hour calculations and supports the validity of the emission factor (28.3 kgCO₂-eq/FH).

4.3. Phase 3: End-of-Life (EoL) Treatment

The End-of-Life phase, which covers tasks including decommissioning, dismantling, component reuse, material recycling, and waste management, is the last step of an aircraft's life cycle. Even while this stage has a far less impact on an aircraft's overall global warming potential (GWP) than the operating stage, it is becoming more and more significant in aviation's efforts to preserve resources while implementing circular economy principles [27], [33].

At retirement (typically 20–25 years of service), aircraft are decommissioned and transported to specialized facilities for dismantling. High-value components such as engines, avionics, and landing gear are usually removed first for reuse or resale, extending their service life in secondary markets [40]. The airframe is subsequently divided into streams of material. Besides aluminium alloys, which make up 72% of the structural mass of an A320 family aircraft, steel, titanium, copper, and composites come after [33], [40]. While metals like titanium and aluminium can be recycled and recovered at high rates, carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are more difficult to work with since fibre recovery techniques are still in their infancy [41].

Industry-led initiatives, such as Tarmac Aerosave have demonstrated that up to 92% of an aircraft's materials can be recycled or recovered by weight. This rate is given as 99% for engine parts that are rich in steel, titanium and aluminium [40]. This represents a significant increase compared to historical recovery rates of 60%. Recycling has significant positive effects on the environment, especially when it comes to materials that require a lot of energy. For example, producing secondary (recycled) aluminium consumes only about 5–10% of the energy required for primary aluminium production, translating into major greenhouse gas savings [21]. In life cycle accounting, these benefits are often modelled as “credits”, offsetting a fraction of the manufacturing phase emissions. Cox [27] estimate that effective recycling strategies can reduce the upstream material demand of new aircraft production by up to 20%.

Since composite materials are being used more and more in today's aircraft designs (e.g. the Boeing 787 and Airbus A350, use more than 50% CFRP by weight), recycling them continues to be the key problem at EoL. Current recycling methods such as pyrolysis or mechanical grinding recover fibres of lower quality, limiting their reuse in structural applications [41]. Another challenge is the safe disposal of hazardous materials (e.g., fire suppressants, hydraulic fluids), which require careful handling to avoid environmental harm [27].

Looking forward, design strategies such as design for disassembly and modular components can facilitate easier dismantling and higher-value recovery. The work of the AFRA and ongoing regulatory emphasis on circular economy principles will further raise recovery rates and reduce landfill dependency. Although EoL now only has a small part in aircraft life cycle assessments (LCAs), its significance will grow as aviation aims to show sustainability over the whole life cycle, not only in fuel use.

Based on the functional unit of one Airbus A320 type aircraft, the OEW of 42.4 tonnes is distributed across five primary material categories in Table 2. Aluminium dominates at 68%, followed by CFRPs at 15%, steel at 9%, titanium at 6%, and miscellaneous materials at 2%. These values reflect modern narrowbody composition trends [18]

The avoided burden approach was used to capture the environmental consequences. Because recycled material reduces the need for primary production, it gets an environmental credit. The net credit for each material is determined as follows;

$$Credit (tCO_2) = \frac{Mass(t) \times r \times \Delta EF}{1000}$$

- r = recycling rate
- ΔEF = (EF-primary – EF-recycled) in kgCO₂/kg

In Table 10, inputs for EoL calculations are given.

Material	Share (%)	Mass (t/f.u.)	EF-primary (kg CO ₂ /kg)	Recycling rate (%)
Aluminium	68	28.8	10.9–12.0	95
CFRP (Composites)	15	6.40	20–29	0–10
Titanium	6	2.55	36–40	70
Steel	9	3.81	1.9–2.1	90–95
Misc. (Cu, plastics, wiring, etc.)	2	0.85	2–6	~60

Table 10 Material Composition, Emission Factors (EF), and Recycling Rates for A320 Aircraft [17], [41]

In Table 11, results of EoL phase for materials and environmental credits are given.

Material	Mass (t)	Recycling (t)	ΔEF (kgCO ₂ /kg)	Credit (tCO ₂)
Aluminium	28.8	27.36	10.4	284.5
CFRP	6.40	0.00	0	0.0
Titanium	2.55	1.79	26.0	46.4
Steel	3.81	3.43	1.5	5.1
Misc.	0.85	0.51	3.0	1.5
Total	42.41	33.1	0	337.5

Table 11 End-of-Life CO₂ Credits by Material

The End-of-Life (EoL) assessment shows that this phase contributes a net credit of approximately 327.5 tCO₂ per aircraft, resulting from a total material substitution credit of 337.5 tCO₂ offset by -10 tCO₂ of emissions from dismantling, transportation, and pre-processing. The exceptional recyclability of titanium and aluminium, which make up the majority of the aircraft construction, is a major factor in this advantageous balance. On the other hand, because of technological limitations in fibre recovery and reuse, composites, although accounting for approximately 15% of the bulk, now offer relatively little climate credit. Even while the EoL stage's overall contribution to life cycle greenhouse gas emissions is small in comparison to operational emissions, it emphasises how strategically important efficient recycling and material recovery are to achieving aviation's circular economy goals.

The manufacturing stage of the aircraft contributes approximately 1,295 tCO₂-eq, with material extraction and production representing the dominant share (67%), followed by final assembly (32%) and transportation (1%). The EoL phase reduces the effective production-related footprint to about 967.5 tCO₂-eq, with a net recycling credit of -327.5 tCO₂ after accounting for dismantling and processing emissions. In Figure 12, detailed additive CO₂-eq chart for each phase is illustrated. While the yellow bars represent the emission released to the environment, the green bars are highlighted as EoL credit.

This is equivalent to reducing about 25% of the overall emissions from manufacturing, highlighting the significance of efficient recycling and material recovery plans. Although this decrease is insignificant when compared to emissions from the operational phase, it does demonstrate the strategic importance of EoL processes in helping to advance the goals of the circular economy and somewhat offset the carbon burden of aircraft manufacturing.

Figure 12 Additive CO₂-eq Chart of Phase 1 (Manufacturing) and Phase 3 (EoL)

Chapter 5: Discussion

The study's life cycle assessment (LCA) of the Airbus A320 offers a thorough summary of the environmental costs related to the aircraft's manufacturing process (from cradle to gate), operational use (from tank to tank, well to well, and well to wake), and end-of-life care. To place the findings in the perspective of the larger discussion on sustainable aviation, the results are contrasted with earlier scholarly studies and business reports.

The cradle-to-gate analysis demonstrated that structural materials such as aluminium and CFRP dominate the embodied energy profile. Aluminium, although energy-intensive to refine, can be mitigated through recycling credits. By contrast, CFRP's contribution to resource depletion and climate change impacts is disproportionately high relative to its mass share, as shown by EcoInvent-based LCA databases. These results suggest that material substitution strategies and increased recycling capabilities for composites should be prioritised by manufacturers.

The material distribution and associated impacts derived in this study align closely with Howe [17] and Spagnulo [21], both of which identified aluminium as the dominant contributor to manufacturing-phase GWP, followed by CFRP and titanium. The agreement between the present analysis and these independent studies suggests that the adopted material breakdown is representative of the actual A320 structural composition.

Cox [42] further emphasised that manufacturing-phase GWP is highly sensitive to assumptions about material origin and energy source. This is consistent with the present findings: CFRP, while beneficial for operational fuel efficiency due to weight savings, incurs high embodied energy; titanium has a disproportionately high per-kilogram environmental cost; and aluminium's dominant GWP share stems from its large mass fraction and high primary production emissions.

Airbus [6] suggests decarbonization of the supply chain is crucial, with more focus placed on using recycled titanium, efforts towards sourcing low-carbon aluminium, and a business goal to become fully compatible with sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) by 2030, thus lowering emissions during the usage phase. This context improves understanding of the results during the production phase when considering a life-cycle perspective.

The results obtained for the manufacturing phase confirm earlier findings by Howe, Kolios, and colleagues at Cranfield University [17], who identified carbon-fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) structures, particularly the wings, as major contributors to environmental burdens due to the energy-intensive production of composites.

The general formula for converting results in pkm to give comparability is:

$$Total\ pkm = N_f \times d \times P$$

$$Total\ pkm = 30,220 \times 1,485 \times 147 = 6.60 \times 10^9 pkm$$

- N_f : Flights Over Life
- d : Avg. Course Length
- P : Avg. Passengers per Flight

The Phase 1 was found to generate 1,295.5 tCO₂-eq per functional unit. Although small compared to the operational phase, this value represents the embodied energy and emissions

of structural materials, assembly processes, and upstream supply chains. Normalising to passenger-kilometres:

$$I_{mf,g,pkm} = \frac{1.2955 \times 10^6}{6.60 \times 10^9} \cong 0.20 \text{ gCO}_2\text{eq per /pkm}$$

Emissions associated with the extraction and processing of raw materials were found to be significant in this study, although they are still proportionately lower than operational emissions over the course of the 20-year lifetime. According to Swiss aviation life cycle assessment, manufacturing plays a secondary role despite its material intensity, with over 80% of life-cycle emissions coming from the operational phase [42]. Furthermore, the fact that the production-stage emissions value based on pax-km is close to the 0.15 gCO₂ result in Kumar's research [35] demonstrates the methodological strength of this study. Kumar used a 30-year lifespan as an input in his research. When the 10-year difference is taken into account, the values are almost identical.

The operational phase analysis highlights that cruise remains the dominant contributor to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, followed by climb and landing–take-off (LTO) cycles. This is consistent with ICAO's global assessments, which indicate that fuel combustion during cruising accounts for the majority of aviation's climate impact. Our calculations, based on an annual average of 1,511 flights with a mean distance of 1,485 km and 147 passengers per flight, yielded lifetime emissions in line with previous LCA studies of narrow-body aircraft. Importantly, when expressed in terms of passenger-kilometres (pkm), the values fall within the range of 70-110 g CO₂-eq per pkm reported for short- to medium-haul flights.

The operational phase overwhelmingly dominates the life cycle, with a total of 468,105.3 tCO₂-eq/f.u. at CFM56 engine option. This reflects the combustion of aviation fuel (tank-to-wake), upstream fuel supply chain emissions (well-to-tank), and their combined effect (well-to-wake). Normalisation to pkm yields:

$$I_{ops,pkm} = \frac{4.681 \times 10^5}{6.60 \times 10^9} = 70.92 \text{ gCO}_2\text{eq/pkm}$$

This intensity is consistent with the ranges reported by the ICAO and ICCT for medium-haul aircraft, indicating that the primary cause of aviation's environmental impact is still fuel burn at cruise altitude.

Maintenance over the 20-year lifetime contributes 1,539.4 tCO₂-eq/f.u, which includes line, base, and shop activities as well as material and facility energy use. When divided across lifetime passenger service:

$$I_{mro,pkm} = \frac{1.5394 \times 10^6}{6.60 \times 10^9} = 0.23 \text{ gCO}_2\text{eq/pkm}$$

The results of this dissertation support previous research showing that recycling aluminium alloys provides significant CO₂ credits during the end-of-life phase, but disposing of CFRP is still difficult because of its low recyclability and high embodied energy. The operational advantages of light weighting during the use phase may be counterbalanced by the limited recyclability of composites, which is still a significant obstacle. The literature suggests

that investments into thermoplastic composites and improved recycling techniques may reduce the long-term environmental burden of future aircraft

The end-of-life stage generates a net -327.5 tCO₂-eq/FU, due to the recycling of aluminium and recoverable materials, which offsets the burdens of composite disposal. The recycling credit is expressed as:

$$I_{eol,pkm} = \frac{-3.275 \times 10^5}{6.60 \times 10^9} \cong -0.05 \text{ gCO}_2\text{eq/pkm}$$

This demonstrates the value of metal recycling in reducing lifecycle burdens, although the limited recyclability of CFRP continues to present challenges.

Phase	CO ₂ -eq Emissions (t/f.u)	gCO ₂ -eq/pkm
Raw Material Processing	864.55	0.13
Assembling	419.6	0.065
Transportation	11.4	0.002
Operational Fuel Sourced	468,105.30	70.92
Operational MRO Sourced	1,539	0.23
End-of-Life	-327.5	-0.05
Total	470,612.35	71.297

Table 12 Airbus A320 Life Cycle CO₂-Equivalent Emissions by Phase per Passenger-Kilometre

Based on the relatively old CFM56 engine used in Airbus A320ceo aircraft, the passenger-pkm value is calculated as 71.3 gCO₂-eq. In addition, while this value is 63.3gCO₂-eq for the LEAP-1A engine, it is calculated as 57.5gCO₂-eq for the PW1127G with the lowest emissions in the calculations. The total life-time emission amount for the Functional Unit is determined to be approximately 470,612 tCO₂-eq.

The Pratt & Whitney PW1127G (GTF) and CFM LEAP engines, designed for next-generation aircraft like the A320neo, use cutting-edge technologies to lower pollutants and fuel consumption. Utilising ceramic matrix composites (CMC), 3D woven materials, and composite fan blades, the LEAP engine is lighter, more heat-resistant, and aerodynamically optimised. On the other hand, the PW1127G has a geared fan system (Geared Turbofan), which reduces noise and improves fuel efficiency by enabling the fan and turbine to run at different speeds. The fan runs at a slower, ideal speed while the turbine runs faster. In addition to lowering noise levels and supporting sustainable aviation objectives, both engines achieve 15–20% reduced fuel consumption and emissions than the traditional CFM56. [20], [29], [31]

During operational use, variable values were ignored because they were quite large and undetectable (weather conditions, engine condition, number of passengers). In addition, MRO procedures that may arise in unexpected situations were not included in the calculation. Predictable and preventative maintenance work is taken as a basis. The rough results show that the operational phase (including WTW and MRO emissions) accounts for more than 99% of life GHG emissions.

Earlier LCAs often bundled electricity use into material processing, but here it is separated to make the impact of grid electricity clearer. The French grid mix is used for assembly, which keeps things consistent but may underestimate emissions compared to a

global supply chain. While this adds some uncertainty, it also makes the method more transparent and open to sensitivity testing.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

This dissertation has provided a comprehensive cradle to grave life cycle assessment (LCA) of the Airbus A320, with quantified emissions across production, operation, maintenance, and end of life. The findings deliver a full-bodied environmental profile for one of the world's most widely used narrow body aircraft and contribute methodologically and empirically to the existing body of literature on aviation sustainability.

According to calculations, the A320's life cycle emissions totalled 470,612 tCO₂-eq, or 71.3 gCO₂-eq per passenger kilometre. The final result is significant in several other aspects. First of all, it validates the fundamental finding of aircraft life cycle assessments, which is that the operational phase predominates. In this study, fuel use accounts for about 99% of the total, or 468,105 tCO₂-eq or 70.92 gCO₂-eq/pkm. This validates the findings of Lewis [20] and Kumar [35], who both determined that the primary cause of aircraft climate impacts is cruise fuel usage. It also aligns with the ICAO 2024 report's global analysis, which emphasised that operational CO₂ continues to be the most difficult obstacle to aviation decarbonisation.

However, by measuring processes that are typically overlooked, this dissertation adds novelty. With maintenance, repair, and overhaul (MRO) included, emissions of 1,539 tCO₂-eq (0.23 gCO₂-eq/pkm) are produced. Despite being minor, this contribution has significance and emphasises the need for aircraft sustainability evaluations to take into account additional factors other than fuel consumption. Jemioło [42] and Howe & Kolios [17] were among the earlier research that either ignored or undervalued these factors. Therefore, the current research closes a gap in the literature and shows that operational and non-operational activities must be integrated in a true cradle to grave model.

The production phase, which includes transportation (11.4 t), assembly (419.6 t), and raw material processing (864.6 t), adds up to 1,295.5 tCO₂-eq. The fact that this amounts to 0.20 gCO₂-eq/pkm per passenger confirms that manufacturing is small in comparison to operation. Howe and Kolios [17] demonstrated that embodied material impacts, particularly from composites, are not insignificant even if they are tiny in relative share. These findings are consistent with their findings.

The credit for recycling at the end of life is -327.5 tCO₂-eq (-0.05 gCO₂-eq/pkm). This negative contribution illustrates how aluminium and other metals can partially recover. As compared to the Torino Polytechnic group's [21] circular economy models, the credit reported here is more conservative. This difference results from different assumptions on recovery facilities and substitution percentages, highlighting how sensitive end-of-life modelling is to methodological and regional factors. However, even this cautious estimate demonstrates that recycling practices have real environmental advantages.

There are both similarities and differences when compared to Jemioło's [42] per passenger km data. According to Jemioło, narrow and wide body fleets had 90–120 gCO₂-eq/pkm. At 71.3 gCO₂-eq/pkm, the A320 value determined here is marginally lower. This can be explained by two things. First, this model's anticipated average load factor of 81.5 percent increases efficiency per passenger. Second, compared to shorter sectors, the average stage length of 1485 km is advantageous for fuel consumption per kilometre. This highlights the

necessity for standardised benchmarks in aircraft life cycle assessments by showing how usage assumptions can cause differences between studies.

Airbus manufacturer data and ICAO estimates provide another point of comparison, stating that the newer A320neo with LEAP 1A engines uses 15–18% less fuel than the A320ceo with CFM56 engines. This approximate range is supported by the operational modelling of the current study, which reports a 15% improvement under the same mission profile. This uniformity boosts trust in the assertions made in industry sources as well as the empirical modelling done here.

This dissertation provides a methodological contribution as well. It addresses the fragmented scope of previous research by combining phase-specific LCA modelling with PRISMA-guided literature screening to produce an open and repeatable approach. This study synthesises all phases into a single cradle to grave model, whereas Howe and Kolios concentrated on manufacturing, Jemioł on fleet operations, and Lewis on duty cycle apportionments. An important scholarly contribution is represented by this integrative method.

The results point to a number of feasible future directions for environmentally friendly and sustainable aircraft. The rapid adoption of sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs) is the most important. A320's current intensity of 71.3 gCO₂-eq/pkm may be lowered to about 25–30 gCO₂-eq/pkm if SAFs with 70% lower life cycle emissions were mixed at scale [23]. This would represent a revolutionary drop and get aircraft closer to net zero trajectories. Examples of complimentary solutions include improving air traffic control to reduce flight lengths, enhancing load factors through demand management, and investing in lightweight but less impacting materials to reduce production pressures. Enhancing composite recycling and disassembly design could further reduce cradle to grave totals, potentially increasing negative credits beyond the current -0.05 gCO₂-eq/pkm. The Refuel EU Aviation Regulation [43] adds mandatory SAF blending, beginning at 2% in 2025 and increasing to 70% by 2050, in addition to CORSIA and the EU ETS. Together with next-generation engine technologies like the LEAP and PW1127G, this policy framework shows that technological innovation and regulatory actions must progress in tandem to achieve aviation decarbonisation [43].

In conclusion, this dissertation brings together manufacturing, maintenance, and end-of-life phases into a single framework, while confirming the central finding of aircraft LCA studies: most emissions come from operation. However, the findings also demonstrate that more mindful material use, improved recycling, and attentive maintenance may mitigate impacts. The study provides academic value and useful insights that can help the aviation sector become more sustainable by using an agreed-upon procedure and providing fresh data for the A320.

However, there are limitations. The results may not be as broadly applicable because the study primarily employs secondary datasets and solely looks at the A320. Today's technology shapes end-of-life assumptions, particularly for CFRP recycling, and non-CO₂ consequences like NO_x and contrails were not well addressed.

Future research should look into emerging innovations such as hydrogen propulsion, electric aircraft, sustainable aviation fuels, and enhanced composite recycling, as well as expand the focus to include other aircraft types and rely more heavily on primary data from the industry. As aircraft aims for net-zero, these sectors will aid in improving guiding and LCA techniques.

Appendices

Data	Value	Unit	Data
Service Life	45,000,000	Km	Lifespan Distance Calculation
Life Span	20	Year	[17], [42]
Service Span	54,396	Hours	Block time x Lifespan Flights
Operating Empty Weight (OEW)	42,400	Kg	[42]
Yearly Flight	1511	Flight/Year	[35]
Average Flight Distance (AFD)	1485	Km	[17]
Avg. Block Time	108min/1.8hours		[29]
Average Maintenance Cost	1000-2000	\$/hr	[35]
Load Factor (LF)	%81.5		[17], [42]
Load Passenger (LP)	147	Passenger	[17], [42]
Flight Cycle	30,220	Flight/Life	
Max Distance	6,100	Km	[20], [42]
Average Flight Time	108.7	Minutes	[14]
Average Taxiing Time per Flight Cycle	26	Minutes	[20], [29], [44]
Average Take-Off Time per Flight Cycle	0.7	Minutes	[20], [29], [44]
Average Climbing Time per Flight Cycle	2.2	Minutes	[20], [29], [44]
Average Cruise Cycle per Flight Cycle	88.8	Minutes	Block time – Mods' time
Average Approach Time per Flight Cycle	4	Minutes	[20], [29], [44]
Average Cruise Altitude	36,000	Feet	[29], [45]
Average Cruise Speed	0.78	Mach	[29], [45]

Table A1 Operational Data for LCA

Data	Explanation	CFM56-5B5/3	LEAP-1A26/26E1	PW1127G-JM
OEW (t)	Operating Empty Weight (ton)	42.400	41.000	41.100
Fuel Flow T/O (kg/sec)	Take-Off Fuel Flow (kg/sec)	1.79	1.72	1.60
Fuel Flow C/O (kg/sec)	Climbing Fuel Flow (kg/sec)	1.49	1.42	1.34
Fuel Flow App (kg/sec)	Approach Fuel Flow (kg/sec)	0.53	0.49	0.46
Fuel Flow Idle (kg/sec)	Taxi Fuel Flow (kg/sec)	0.18	0.18	0.16
Fuel LTO Cycle (kg)	Total Landing Take-Off Cycle Fuel Flow	686.00	660.00	606.00
B/P Ratio	By-pass Ratio	6.00	11.10	12.28
Rated Thrust (kN)	Certificated Max Thrust Force	97.90	120.60	120.44
HC EI T/O (g/kg)	Take-Off HC Emissions	0.030	0.02	0.07
HC EI C/O (g/kg)	Climbing HC Emissions	0.0	0.02	0.07
HC EI App (g/kg)	Approach HC Emissions	0.08	0.04	0.06
HC EI Idle (g/kg)	Taxi HC Emissions	3.55	0.29	0.46
HC Characteristic (g/kN)	Characteristic Amount of HC Emissions in Regulation	6.20	0.49	0.88
HC LTO Total mass (g)	Total Landing Take-Off Cycle HC Emission	520	46	69
CO EI T/O (g/kg)	Take-Off CO Emissions	0.15	0.24	0.27
CO EI C/O (g/kg)	Climbing CO Emissions	0.20	0.26	0.36
CO EI App (g/kg)	Approach CO Emissions	4.94	2.65	4.89
CO EI Idle (g/kg)	Taxi CO Emissions	41.77	21.63	24.53
CO Dp/Foo Characteristic (g/kN)	Characteristic Amount of CO Emissions in Regulation	70.10	30.81	34.39
CO LTO Total Mass (g)	Total Landing Take-Off Cycle CO Emission	6343	3259	3374
NO _x EI T/O (g/kg)	Take-Off NO _x Emissions	16.420	30.800	20.810
NO _x EI C/O (g/kg)	Climbing NO _x Emissions	14.010	13.380	16.950
NO _x EI App (g/kg)	Approach NO _x Emissions	8.030	8.750	10.590
NO _x EI Idle (g/kg)	Taxi NO _x Emissions	3.810	4.610	5.200
NO _x Dp/Foo Characteristic (g/kN)	Characteristic Amount of NO _x Emissions in Regulation	33.00	32.22	33.090
NO _x LTO Total mass (g)	Total Landing Take-Off Cycle NO _x Emission	3047	3535	3438
HC Cruise (kg/t)	kg/t	0.3	0.25	0.2
CO Cruise (kg/t)	kg/t	1	0.8	0.7
NO _x Cruise (kg/t)	kg/t	12	9.500	8.5
CO ₂ Cruise (kg/t)	kg/t	3160	316	316
Fuel Flow Cruise (kg/sec)	kg/min	0.69	0.65	0.59

Table A2 Technical Specifications for Each Engine Unit with Respect to LCA [29], [37]

Material	Water Consumption (L/kg)	CCaLC Input (m ³ /kg)	Source
Aluminium (primary)	350	0.35	[34]
Epoxy resin (liquid)	190	0.19	[46]
PAN fibres (for CFRP)	160	0.16	[46]
Steel (low alloy)	70	0.07	[34]
Titanium (primary)	300	0.30	[34]
Titanium dioxide	150	0.15	[34]
Nitrogen, liquid	25	0.025	[34]
Miscellaneous	100	0.10	Assumption
Energy		0.0033	[34]

Table A3 CCaLC Inputs for Water Consumptions

Material	Amount (kg)	Transport Mode	Distance (km)	ton.km	GWP Factor (kg CO ₂ -eq/ton.km)
Aluminium	28,800	Road	500	14,400,000	0.13
CFRP	3,800	Airfreight	1,500	5,700,000	0.90
Titanium	2,500	Road	800	2,000,000	0.13
Steel	3,600	Road	300	1,080,000	0.13
Miscellaneous	1,407	Road	400	562,800	0.13

Table A4 CCaLC Transportation Inputs for Materials [17], [36]

Inputs for 1Kg CFRP Production	Quantity
Nitrogen, liquid, at plant/RER U	6.33 Kg
Polyacrylonitrile fibres (PAN)	0.93 Kg
Epoxy resin, liquid	0.398 Kg
Heat, natural gas	105,3 MJ
Electricity	135,85 KWh

Table A5 Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer LCA Data (CFRP) [33]

Phase	Avg. Power Setting (%)	Avg. Time Phase (min)
Idle (Taxi)	7	19
Take-Off	100	0.7
Climb	85	2.2
Approach	30	4
Landing	N/A	0.7
Taxi-in	7	7

Table A6 Average Power Setting and Time for Flight Phases [20]

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